

Research Article

Experimental Analysis of Crystallinity and Mechanical Properties for Fused Filament Printed Polyetherketone Composites

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The objective of this article is to examine the impacts of molybdenum disulphide (MoS_2) and graphite-filled (Gr) polyetheretherketone (PEEK) composites that have been fabricated through 3D printing on their mechanical properties and crystallinity. Seven samples and thirty-five dog bones were produced using different filament strands to conduct the analysis. Before extrusion into filaments, the solid lubricants, MoS_2 , and graphite were uniformly dispersed within the PEEK through mechanical blending. At a concentration of 10 wt.%, the PEEK/ MoS_2 composites exhibited the highest tensile strength, measuring approximately 104 MPa, while the PEEK/Gr composites displayed the lowest tensile strength at the same concentration, approximately 36 MPa. In addition, the PEEK/ MoS_2 composites demonstrated better elongation, approximately 4.7%, compared to the PEEK/Gr composites, which exhibited approximately 2.3% elongation. X-ray diffraction (XRD) data revealed that neither MoS_2 nor graphite significantly interacted with the PEEK matrix. The degree of crystallinity, as determined by density matrices, indicated that the printed PEEK composites possessed a higher level of crystallinity, approximately 62% at a concentration of 5 wt.%, than the calculated values. This suggests that the filament-making and 3D printing processes had an annealing effect. The significance of solid lubricant content and dispersion in shaping the mechanical properties and crystal formation of 3D-printed PEEK composites is emphasized in this study. Furthermore, this research provides valuable insights for optimizing PEEK-based materials for various applications.

1. Introduction

In the era of Industry 4.0, significant strides have been made in innovative manufacturing methods, unlocking novel avenues for product design and unprecedented efficiencies in production. Traditional manufacturing techniques, renowned for achieving high production rates, precise control over material properties, and cost competitiveness, are being complemented by the emergence of additive manufacturing (AM), also known as 3D printing. AM offers unique advantages, including the capacity to fabricate intricate geometries and customized designs with minimal reliance on specialized tooling or the generation of material waste. This renders AM particularly well suited for applications in

prototyping, small-scale production, and the accelerated development of new products. [1, 2].

AM has revolutionized the manufacturing industry by offering innovative and efficient ways to create complex parts in various industries. By integrating AM with conventional methods, manufacturers can harness the synergistic strengths of both approaches, resulting in heightened flexibility, enhanced operational efficiency, and a deeper wellspring of innovation in the domain of polymers and composites. The recent advancements in AM technologies have ushered in shorter design and prototyping phases during new product development, giving rise to advanced product designs and tooling concepts. Furthermore, the evolving market dynamics have made 3D printers

increasingly accessible across various sectors, encompassing research, industrial, and consumer applications [1].

One of the cheapest AM techniques is material extrusion (ME) of fused filament fabrication (FFF), also known as fused deposition modeling (FDM). FFF has gained popularity due to its advantages over traditional manufacturing processes [3–5].

The Stratasys corporation patented ME and FFF. FFF is a method that deposits layers of molten thermoplastic material to produce 3D objects. Layer height, nozzle diameter, printing speed, and extrusion temperature are the main factors that affect the process [6].

FFF offers manufacturers the freedom of accessible design, enabling the creation of complex parts that were previously challenging or impossible to manufacture. With FFF, there is no need for moulds or tools, reducing the cost and time associated with traditional manufacturing processes [7–9]. In addition, FFF allows control of some mechanical properties such as porosity, structure, and crystallinity by manipulating contents and components such as fibre volume and orientation within its manufacturing limits [10–12].

FFF, which uses a thermoplastic filament as a raw material, is one of the most appreciated additive manufacturing techniques [13, 14]. The FFF technique is an appealing approach for producing high-performance components utilising plastic composite materials because of its inherent benefits, including price, speed, and ease of use [15–17].

A trend in FFF is the improvement of printer capabilities, such as increased speed and resolution, by continuous advancements in technology and decreasing costs. This allows faster and more precise parts production, reducing lead times and increasing efficiency [18, 19]. There are certain drawbacks to consider with FFF techniques, though. Lamination, a term for visible layer lines, may be present, necessitating further postprocessing for smoother finishes. When compared to other approaches, layer-by-layer construction may have inferior strength. Large-scale manufacturing is constrained by the ME method's slower speed and size limits. Intricate designs can make it difficult to remove support structures, possibly necessitating physical labour and equipment [20].

ME represents the most readily accessible 3D printing technology currently available, and it is particularly well suited for the fabrication of functional components from functionally graded materials (FGMs). This category of components, characterized by intentional variations in structure, chemistry, microstructure, and properties within a single part, represents the forefront of manufacturing technology. It holds great promise for diverse applications spanning multiple industries, including but not limited to medical devices and aerospace [1, 21, 22].

In the context of polymer in AM trends, creating functional parts necessitates using a semicrystalline polymer to deliberately alter material properties across a spectrum ranging from maximum to minimum achievable crystallinity. This requirement eliminates the most common ME printing materials, such as ABS and nylon, as they are

classified as amorphous polymers. PLA, another frequently used ME material, is a semicrystalline polymer; however, its crystallinity level is relatively low, and the temperature range within which its crystalline properties can be modified is limited, making it unsuitable for creating a demonstrable ME FGM [1, 23]. Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) demonstrates significant crystalline characteristics and boasts a broad temperature range within which its material attributes can be adjusted. When a semicrystalline polymer like PEEK is subjected to the cooling process from a molten state or heating from an amorphous solid state, it undergoes crystallization.

PEEK is a high-performance thermoplastic material widely used as a matrix within the burgeoning thermoplastic composite industry. Originating in the 1980s through the efforts of Imperial Chemical Industries, PEEK continues to exhibit considerable promise due to its nonreactive nature towards chemical reagents, remarkable heat resistance, exceptional elastic modulus, and outstanding durability in thermally oxidative environments. PEEK is synthesized through a biphenyl (hydroquinone) reaction with a fluorinated aromatic compound in a polar aprotic solvent, diphenyl sulfone. This synthesis's preference for fluorinated derivatives arises from their superior reactivity and heightened electronegativity relative to chlorinated derivatives [2, 24].

Furthermore, studies have indicated that components manufactured through the FFF process using filled polymers exhibit enhanced mechanical performance and have the potential to acquire novel and improved attributes that are not observed in unfilled polymers or conventional production methods [1, 24–30].

Due to its superior mechanical and chemical qualities, PEEK composite is currently a preferred option in today's 3D manufacturing tasks. Due to the filling process of impregnating polymers, reheating during the FFF techniques changes the crystal formation of semicrystalline polymers like PEEK.

However, it is noted that 3D printing can be difficult due to the high heat temperature requirement of PEEK composites [4, 31–33].

Most recent research carried out by other researchers focused on the traditional way of manufacturing, and little attention or no attention is given to the effect of solid lubricants on the FFF-printed polymer's crystal level or content.

Multiple variables, including the composition ratio, filler type, printing temperature, and manufacturing methodologies, exert an impact on the interplay between crystallinity levels and mechanical attributes in polymers. Furthermore, it is worth emphasizing that as crystallinity levels increase, tensile properties tend to exhibit enhancement. However, it is important to note that the specific influence of crystal content on tensile properties may vary due to factors such as the nature of the polymer, mixture proportions, distribution, and the conditions associated with thermal processing [6, 34–37].

In recent times, comprehensive investigations have been scarce into FFF's mechanical and tribological characteristics utilising PEEK composites. Notably, these studies have often

overlooked the influence of filler materials, particularly solid lubricants, on the percentage of crystalline structure within the composite produced via the FFF technique [4, 38, 39]. Hence, this research endeavour aims to investigate and elucidate the influence of solid lubricant variants and their respective quantities on the formation of crystalline content within FFF-fabricated PEEK composites. Furthermore, this study seeks to comprehensively analyze the impact of crystalline content on the mechanical properties of the FFF-printed PEEK composite.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Sample Preparation. Inorganic graphite (Gr.), molybdenum disulphide (MoS_2), and PEEK 45 nanoparticles with average diameters of $45\ \mu\text{m}$, $100\ \mu\text{m}$, and $150\ \mu\text{m}$, respectively, were provided by Kayla Africa, a supplier and distributor at the Vaal University of Technology. The matrix (PEEK) 450 delivered by the Kayla Africa supplier and distributor has a data sheet containing this information: average molecular weight (MW) of $44,000\ \text{g/mol}$, glass temperature (T_g) of 143°C , and melting temperature (T_m) of 343°C . A particle size distribution was carried out for each powder to ascertain that the powder supplied was below 300 microns to avoid agglomeration.

Each solid lubricant, namely, molybdenum disulphide (MoS_2) and graphite (Gr) of volume 3 wt.%, 5 wt.%, and 10 wt.%, was mixed differently with the PEEK using a mechanical blender shown in Figure 1. The mechanical mixing first dispersed the lubricants uniformly using a mechanical blender before extruding them into filaments.

The powder generated from the mixing and blending was further made into filament using a Filastruder filament-making machine. The Filastruder was initially modified to sustain a higher temperature than its manufactured limit by replacing the default PTFE-insulated Type K thermocouple with an E3D glass fibre-insulated Type K cartridge thermocouple and increasing the power supply input from 12 volts to 20 volts to increase the heating capacity of the filament maker extruder. The Filastruder was PID-tuned to handle the temperature and torque (speed of screw rotation) during extrusion to reduce the effect of die swelling. A top table set-up called Filawinder was used to reel in the filament produced on a spool. The Filawinder was employed to mitigate the die swelling by using an optical laser to monitor and correct the filament diameter by the variance of tensioning or compressing the filament by the speed of motors. The Filastruder was configured to the highest possible temperature of about 420°C with a single screw rotating and a nozzle diameter of 1.75 mm.

A control filament of pure PEEK was also extruded. Then, 7 groups of the extruded filament strands were printed using a retrofitted Fabbster, an FFF technology printer. The printing parameter was set using open-sourced 3D Printer Slicr software, as tabulated in Table 1. The printing bed was heated to a temperature of 120°C , and the room temperature was 23°C .

FIGURE 1: The filament-making process.

TABLE 1: Information incorporated in slicer file for 3D printer.

Printing parameters	Values
Printing speed	20 mm/s
Layer thickness	$300\ \mu\text{m}$
Raster angle	$0/90^\circ$
Infill density	80%
Nozzle temperature	330°C
External perimeter	3 times

5 tensile dog bones from each of the 7 groups of filaments produced were printed to make 35 pieces per Type 1 of the ASTM D638 standard for plastic tensile testing using the build orientation and printing direction as shown in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2: (a) The computer 3D representation of dog bone; (b) the printing and building direction of the tensile dog bone.

2.2. Printer Modifications. The Fabbster 3D printer was modified for printing PEEK samples. The printer was initially designed for polymer printing and had a temperature limit of 280°C for ABS. The hot end temperature was increased to 470°C to enable PEEK printing, and the bed temperature was set to 150°C. The modifications included replacing the stock hot end with a micro-Swiss direct drive mounted on aluminium as shown in Figure 3.

The printer's software was modified using VS-code with PlatformIO, and the firmware was edited from the Marlin 2 repository. The control board was upgraded to the MKS Rumba 32-bit controller, enabling heat bed configuration, high-temperature hot end, and sensor-less homing, eliminating the need for optical or mechanical end stops. The microstepping of the motors was set to 1/32 for each axis, and the motor current was limited to 750 mA to prevent overheating of the stepper motors. The printer's axes were equipped with dual stepper motors, and sensor-less homing was activated using the TMC2226 driver.

Mechanical modifications involved changing the extrusion system from Bowden tube style (shown in Figure 4(a)) to direct drive (shown in Figure 3) using custom brackets. Figure 4(b) shows the custom 3D-designed bracket used for hanging the micro-Swiss drive. The printer was successfully retrofitted to handle high-temperature PEEK printing with improved control and safety features.

2.3. Characterisation. The mechanical tests were conducted on plastic samples using an Inston 3369 universal testing machine (UTM) equipped with an optical extensometer. The UTM was loaded with a 30 kN cell, following the ASTM D 638-14 test standards. The tests were performed at room temperature (23°C) and atmospheric pressure (101.33 kPa), with a constant crosshead speed of 5 mm/min, per ASTM standards for plastics. Instron software determined tensile strength and elongation values and saved them as a CSV file.

X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD) was performed on both the original PEEK polymer and the manufactured sample to examine the impact of solid lubricant on the sample's crystallinity. The Empyrean diffractometer was used, employing Cu K α radiation with 45 KV and 40 mA electrical charge, measuring within 5° to 35°. The degree of crystallinity (X_c) was calculated using the Hermans-Weidinger

diagrammatic method, as described by Gusev (1978) [40] in the following equation:

$$X_c = \frac{A_C}{A_C + A_a} \times 100. \quad (1)$$

X_c represents the degree of crystallinity, A_C is the Area of crystal peaks in the XRD, and A_a is the Area of amorphous peaks in the XRD. The calculated X_c value was then compared to the theoretical crystallinity level obtained from polymer density calculations, as given by the following equation:

$$\rho_{th} = (\rho_p \times W_p) + (\rho_s \times W_s), \quad (2)$$

where ρ_{th} is the theoretical density of filled PEEK, ρ_p is the density of PEEK ($1.32 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg/cm}^3$), W_p is the weight ratio of PEEK, ρ_s is the density of the solid lubricant, and W_s is the weight ratio of the solid lubricant. The density matrix (ρ_m) was derived from Agarwal et al.'s composite analysis textbook (2006) by using the following equation [41]:

$$\rho_m (1 - W_s) = \rho_{th} - (\rho_s \times W_s). \quad (3)$$

To determine the level of crystallinity in the printed PEEK, (4) was employed, using the density matrix (ρ_m) from Bhuiyan's report (2020) on crystallinity and amorphous measuring techniques [42].

$$X_c = \frac{\rho_m - \rho_a}{\rho_c - \rho_a}. \quad (4)$$

In this equation, X_c represents the degree of crystallinity, ρ_c is the density of PEEK in its crystalline phase (1.4 g/cm^3), ρ_a is the density of PEEK in its amorphous phase (1.263 g/cm^3), and ρ_m is the density matrix. Based on supplier information, the densities of graphite and MoS₂ used were 1.226 g/cm^3 and 5.06 g/cm^3 , respectively.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Mechanical Properties. The addition of graphite to PEEK (Gr./PEEK) led to a nonlinear decrease in tensile strength within the weight fraction range of 3% to 10%. A similar downward trend was observed for elongation at break as shown in Figures 5 and 6. On the other hand, Young's modulus exhibited a nonlinear increase. The decrease in elongation at break can be attributed to the brittleness and

FIGURE 3: (a) The front and (b) the side view of the assembled and modified printer with micro-Swiss direct drive.

FIGURE 4: (a) The default printer style in Bowden tube configuration and (b) the custom brackets used to mount the micro-Swiss drive.

FIGURE 5: Tensile strength of PEEK, Gr/PEEK, and MoS₂/PEEK.

agglomeration of graphite within the PEEK matrix, which aligns with findings by Chen et al. [43]. The declining tensile strength is also likely due to the agglomeration of graphite

particles within the PEEK matrix, possibly caused by the significant difference in particle size and density between the two materials.

FIGURE 6: Elongation at break of PEEK, Gr/PEEK, and MoS₂/PEEK.

Moreover, the reduction in tensile strength could be influenced by decreased adhesion forces between PEEK molecules and the further oxidation of graphite during filament production and printing. Both PEEK composites showed a sharp drop in elongation between 0 wt.% and 3 wt.%, followed by a gradual reduction. The increased presence of solid lubricants resulted in higher brittleness and weaker interfacial bonds within the PEEK matrix. In addition, incorporating solids in PEEK could reduce elongation or crack initiation due to agglomeration.

Conversely, the incorporation of MoS₂ into PEEK (MoS₂/PEEK) showed a nonlinear rise in tensile strength and Young's modulus, reaching a maximum increase of 61%. This improvement can be attributed to the even distribution of MoS₂ within the PEEK matrix, which aligns with findings from a study by Yan et al. on MoS₂/PEEK [44].

MoS₂/PEEK exhibited superior mechanical properties compared to PEEK/Gr. The highest recorded tensile strength was 101 MPa for a 10 wt.% MoS₂ content. The addition of both solid lubricants in 3D-printed PEEK had distinct effects on tensile strength. However, it should be noted that the experimental tensile strength showed a slight reduction compared to the known theoretical values, which is consistent with trends observed in other studies on 3D-printed polymers. Such a reduction in tensile strength is attributed to the inherent characteristics of 3D-printed objects, which typically exhibit 70% to 80% of the tensile strength of their traditionally fabricated counterparts [30, 45].

Regarding Young's modulus, representing the ratio of stress to strain with an elastic limit, there were different responses to the two solid lubricants. Figure 7 illustrates the behaviour of PEEK with the two solids. The control 3D-printed PEEK had a modulus of elasticity of 3.89 GPa. Gr/PEEK showed an almost linear increase in Young's modulus with increasing additive fractions. In contrast, Young's modulus for MoS₂/PEEK reached a plateau

between 3 wt.% and 5 wt.%. The addition of solid lubricants increased the stiffness of the PEEK matrix, resulting in a consistent rise in the elastic modulus of the printed PEEK composite. The highest recorded modulus values were 4.49 GPa for Gr./PEEK and 4.48 GPa for MoS₂/PEEK at a 10 wt.% filler content, surpassing the control sample. This increase is attributed to the enhanced stiffness of the solids as their content increases.

Adding MoS₂ to PEEK enhances stress strength, particularly when the loading surpasses 3 wt.%. This improvement is likely because of MoS₂'s higher matrix density and better dispersion within PEEK. On the other hand, the inclusion of graphite fillers shows a consistent decline in strength, indicating agglomeration within the PEEK matrix. Studies by Fu et al. (2008) and Chen et al. (2018) have shown that adding graphite beyond 0.3 wt.% in PEEK leads to agglomeration, resulting in weaker bonds and reduced fatigue resistance [46, 47]. Fu et al. [47] further emphasized the significance of matrix interfacial adhesion in determining the tensile strength of polymer composites, as it influences the effectiveness of stress transfer between fillers and the polymer. MoS₂/PEEK exhibits improved stress strength, likely due to its higher matrix density and dispersion, while graphite fillers tend to agglomerate, weakening the material. The interfacial adhesion between the matrix and fillers plays a crucial role in determining the overall tensile strength of composite materials.

3.2. Crystallinity. The diffraction peaks at 18.79°, 20.93°, 22.79°, and 28.83° on planes 110, 111, 200, and 210 indicate that the printed PEEK has an orthorhombic cell configuration as shown in Figure 8. This finding aligns with previous studies by Binling et al. (2018) and Jiang et al. (2021) on PEEK polymer [43, 44, 48].

Adding MoS₂ to PEEK resulted in XRD curves plotted in Figure 9 for 3 wt.%, 5 wt.%, and 10 wt.% MoS₂. PEEK typically exhibits semicrystalline properties with intensity deflections in the 2θ range of 18° to 30°. The addition of MoS₂ produced a deflection at around 13° on plane 200, indicating lower crystallinity levels in the filled PEEK. The peaks of the MoS₂-filled PEEK shifted slightly to the right, indicating the presence of compressive strain. The appearance of a new peak around 13° on plane 200 in the PEEK/MoS₂ XRD graph suggests no significant chemical reaction between MoS₂ and PEEK during the filamentation extrusion and printing process. The trend observed is like findings in other studies on MoS₂ XRD patterns.

Adding Gr. to the PEEK followed a similar trend to the PEEK/MoS₂, as depicted in Figure 10. The graphite-filled PEEK displayed an additional peak at around 26° on plane 002, indicating no significant chemical reaction between PEEK and graphite. The elongation of the graphite peak in PEEK increased with higher graphite ratios, like in previous studies on graphene and graphite oxides.

The Hermans-Weidinger diagrammatic method was employed to determine the degree of crystallinity. The peaks' width, height, and regions under the curve were analysed using the peaks analyser function in the Origin plotter

FIGURE 7: Young's modulus of PEEK, Gr/PEEK, and MoS₂/PEEK.

FIGURE 9: The X-ray diffraction graphs of PEEK/MoS₂ at 3 wt.%, 5 wt.%, and 10 wt.%.

FIGURE 8: The X-ray diffraction pattern PEEK.

FIGURE 10: The X-ray diffraction graphs of PEEK/Gr at 3 wt.%, 5 wt.%, and 10 wt.%.

software. Table 2 and Figure 11 present the experimental data for the degree of crystallinity and the overall graph area obtained from the XRD analysis or graphs.

In theory, incorporating fillers into any polymer typically results in a linear increase in the material's density. When MoS₂ is added, the composite's density is significantly higher than that of the graphite-filled counterpart, leading to an improvement in density of approximately 50% compared to the MoS₂ alone as shown in Table 3 and Figure 12.

The density matrix of both solids within the PEEK matrix decreases nonlinearly and is inversely related to the composite density. Theoretically, the degree of crystallinity depends on the density matrix; as the solids in PEEK increase, the amorphous content in the composite polymer also increases. The PEEK/Gr. exhibited the lowest degree of

TABLE 2: The experimental data for the degree of crystallinity and overall graph area derived from the XRD area.

Solid lubricant weight ratio (%)	Area of crystallinity (mm ²)	Total area (mm ²)	Degree of crystallinity (%)
PEEK	4981.35	9047.282	55.06
3 wt.% MoS ₂	3803.15	5715.375	66.54
5 wt.% MoS ₂	4003.47	5715.375	70.05
10 wt.% MoS ₂	3860.75	5715.375	67.55
3 wt.% Gr	3526.59	10129.925	34.82
5 wt.% Gr	4257.31	10129.925	42.03
10 wt.% Gr	4008.35	10129.925	39.57

FIGURE 11: The experimental degree of crystallinity of both filled PEEK and unfilled PEEK.

FIGURE 12: The calculated degree of crystallinity from density matrices.

TABLE 3: The theoretically derived density, density matrix, and crystallinity at different weight ratios of MoS₂ and Gr.

Solid lubricant percentage (%)	Degree of crystallinity (%)
PEEK	41.606
3 wt.% MoS ₂	39.950
5 wt.% MoS ₂	43.911
10 wt.% MoS ₂	38.362
3 wt.% Gr	35.285
5 wt.% Gr	30.849
10 wt.% Gr	10.787

crystallinity, approximately 11%. This decrease directly influenced the tensile strength and elongation at the break of the composite material.

4. Conclusion

The following conclusions were drawn based on the findings of this study:

- (i) Generally, the MoS₂-filled PEEK composite demonstrated the greatest tensile strength, reaching around

104 MPa at a concentration of 10 wt.%. Conversely, the graphite-filled PEEK composite displayed the lowest tensile strength, measuring approximately 36 MPa at the same concentration. It is essential to highlight that these values represent the experiment's highest and lowest recorded tensile strengths.

- (ii) The addition of both lubricants resulted in a reduction in the elongation at failure. The MoS₂-lubricated PEEK exhibited an almost plateaued effect, maintaining an elongation of approximately 4.7% at a concentration of 10 wt.%. Conversely, the graphite-lubricated PEEK experienced a more significant decline in elongation, reaching about 2.3% at the same concentration.
- (iii) At a concentration of 3 wt.%, the MoS₂-filled PEEK exhibited the lowest Young's modulus of elasticity, measuring 3.95 GPa. This value is slightly lower than Young's modulus of 3.99 GPa recorded for graphite-filled PEEK at the same concentration.
- (iv) Printed PEEK's mechanical strength and crystallinity vary depending on the lubricant type and

mixing ratios. Graphite lubricant was theorised to agglomerate after 5 wt.%, whereas MoS₂ does not suggest such agglomeration up to 10 wt.%.

- (v) The X-ray diffraction (XRD) data of printed pure PEEK shows an orthorhombic array at planes 110, 111, 200, and 210 at planes 19°, 21°, 23°, and 29°, which is the indication that the printed PEEK is in a semicrystalline phase. New crystalline peaks were created at plane 200 at 13° and 002 at 26° for MoS₂ and Gr., respectively, with no existing PEEK peak destroyed, indicating no significant reaction with the solid lubrication.
- (vi) The crystallinity level is higher than the calculated theoretical values, with an average differential of 25% for every weight ratio. These higher values suggest the annealing effect from reheating during filament-making and 3D printing processes. The highest value recorded was at 5 wt.% MoS₂ filling valued at 71% compared to the plain-controlled pure PEEK at 55%.

In summary, the research emphasized the importance of the solid lubricant content and its dispersion in shaping the mechanical properties and level of crystal formation in 3D-printed PEEK composites.

Data Availability

The data used to support the findings of this study are included in the article.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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